

Comparing Open-Source Record Linkage Software to Existing Approaches: A Case Study Using Census Data¹

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Abstract

The U.S. Census Bureau has used entity resolution, also referred to as record linkage or deduplication, for the decennial censuses and other programs such as post-enumeration surveys for several decades. In particular, entity resolution was used on names and common characteristics in the 2020 Census to deduplicate census responses and to link people rostered in the Post-Enumeration Survey (PES) to people enumerated in the Census. In preparation for the 2030 Census, the Decennial Census research agenda includes assessing different record linkage methodology and software. This paper discusses and compares BigMatch, which is a matching software developed at the Census Bureau, against two recent options of open-source software, fastLink and Splink. This paper provides results such as metrics of accuracy measured against 2020 PES clerically reviewed data, for each software.

Keywords: Record Linkage, Entity Resolution, Expectation-Maximization Algorithm, Post-Enumeration Survey, Decennial Census, BigMatch, fastLink, Splink

1. Background

Since the 1980s, the U.S. Census Bureau has used the Fellegi-Sunter (F-S) record linkage framework to perform large-scale record linkage and deduplication tasks for its data [3,8]. Over this period, William Winkler and William Yancey developed a C based application called BigMatch that utilized the F-S framework [8]. BigMatch was used in the 2020 Census and the Post-Enumeration Survey (PES). In the 2020 Census, BigMatch was used to determine duplicate respondents by performing probabilistic record linkage on the census's person files. In the 2020 PES, BigMatch determined links between an independently rostered set of people and housing units, and the corresponding census-enumerated people and housing units, to measure coverage in the census.

The F-S framework establishes the record linkage problem by generating a probability or match score for the pairwise comparison of any two records, conditioned on the agreement pattern across a set of attributes that both records have in common. Useful attributes for person matching include: first name, middle initial, last name, birthdate, and sex. For a record linkage task, the number of comparisons scales by the number of records in file A multiplied by the number of records in file B. For a deduplication task, each record in file A would be compared to all other records in A (i.e., size of file A choose two comparisons). For large files the total number of comparisons becomes computationally hard, and the number of pairwise comparisons to be computed would scale quadratically. Therefore, the number of comparisons must be reduced to link files at the scale required. Blocking is a process of grouping records by similar attributes before trying to link the records, to reduce the total number of pairwise comparisons computed. Conditional independence across matching attributes is assumed in the traditional application of the F-S framework, and in our testing. There are applications of a Bayesian F-S framework such as Fortini [4], but to our

¹ The views expressed are those of the authors and not those of the U.S. Census Bureau. The Census Bureau's Disclosure Review Board and Disclosure Avoidance Officers have reviewed this information product for unauthorized disclosure of confidential information and have approved the disclosure avoidance practices applied to this release. (Data Management System (DMS) number: P-7530562, Disclosure Review Board (DRB) Approval Number: CBDRB-FY24-0390.)

knowledge there are no software under this construction that has proven to scale to a nationwide census level of deduplication.

The purpose of the 2020 PES was to measure the coverage of the 2020 Census. This was done by independently rostering people in the 50 states, the District of Columbia, and Puerto Rico, and matching them to the people who were enumerated in the census. The P sample refers to the set of independently rostered people in sampled areas around the country. The E sample is the set of census enumerations in the same sampled areas. The Census Unedited File (CUF) is the set of census enumerations from the decennial census and is the source of the E sample. The PES's matching procedure identified duplicates in the P and E samples and performed record linkage between the P sample and CUF, observing that the CUF contains the E sample as a subset. Note that we matched to the CUF in this step because P-sample records could link to census responses outside of the E-sample areas. The PES began its linkage with the computer matching unit. Then, clerical staff reviewed the computer links and searched for matches missed by the computer to produce a final set of links [6]. However, for this paper we show only the results from deduplicating the E-sample set of census enumerated person records.

The BigMatch software has several notable features in its implementation of the F-S framework. BigMatch has four types of comparisons that can be used for selected attributes: exact string comparison, string comparison using the Jaro-Winkler comparator for partial string comparison, numerical comparison for age, and numerical comparison for year [5,7]. The Jaro-Winkler string comparator is a fuzzy string comparator like the Jaro and Demaru-Levenstein comparators. The Jaro-Winkler string comparator gives more weight to string scores that have agreement with the first four characters of strings being compared. The BigMatch software can set up complex blocking schemes with multiple blocking passes using filtering. Filtering is done if a comparison in a prior blocking pass has a match score higher than that pass's cutoff, then that comparison link will be filtered out of subsequent blocking passes preventing redundant links from being printed. For attributes that would use string comparison such as a first or last name, BigMatch uses the Jaro-Winkler string comparison metric with a piecewise linear transformation function that sets the partial agreement weight. BigMatch is designed to hold one file in system memory and link those records to the records of another file(s), bringing those records in and out of memory in a way that allows for efficient handling of memory resources. BigMatch is written as a single-threaded application. This is one of its limitations but can be mitigated by breaking up the linking tasks into many jobs and calling the BigMatch application iteratively.

FastLink is an R package developed by Ted Enamorado, Ben Fifield, and Kosuke Imai in 2017 [2]. FastLink's implementation of the F-S framework has three main advantages over BigMatch. First, fastLink is able to distribute the pairwise comparison computations for blocks of records with similar attributes. In theory this would enable scaling more efficiently for large record linkage tasks. Second, fastLink can learn optimized model parameters using the Expectation-Maximization (E-M) algorithm. Third, fastLink's likelihood function includes additional model parameters that account for attributes with missing at random data. For example, middle names are sometimes blank in the person record. BigMatch is a single-threaded application, which does not have an E-M algorithm as a feature, and attributes must be manually set to assign a zero weight or a full disagreement weight for attributes that have missing values. For attributes that can have partial agreement, fastLink will set levels of agreement. These levels of agreement will contribute to the overall match score for a comparison between two records.

Splink is a Python package developed by the United Kingdom Ministry of Justice Analytical Services in 2020 [1]. Splink's implementation of the F-S framework is based on the same methodology that fastLink uses. It adds features for scaling to large-scale record linkage tasks and customization on how links are produced. The Splink software allows for multiple SQL backend database types enabling the software to scale through distributive computing on multiple database platforms such as: DuckDB, Spark, Athena, SQLite, and PostgreSQL. For the tests performed in this paper we only used the DuckDB backend. The DuckDB backend was able to perform the record linkage on the data that we used but was limited in its ability to learn on the data. This will be

discussed later on in the methodology section. Splink also provides a toolbox of analytic functions to determine characteristics about the data before linking.

2. Methodology

We assessed the three software on their ability to deduplicate a sample of census enumerations. The sample consisted of person enumerations within each basic collection unit (BCU)² that was included in the E sample. As part of 2020 PES matching operations, these person enumerations were deduplicated and links were clerically reviewed. For this research, we considered these links to be our truth set. We excluded any links that were made to census enumerations that were outside of the E-sample BCUs because we did not have a complete 'true' set of links for these enumerations. The PES operations matched enumerations in Puerto Rico and the rest of the United States as separate universes, so we separated our test the same way. Our sample set of enumerations in the rest of the United States (including Washington D.C.) consisted of 1,167,705 records with 3,941 true links among them. The Puerto Rico enumerations consisted of 33,254 person records with 1,125 true links among them.

The blocking scheme implemented by the three software was the same scheme that was used in the 2020 PES matching. That blocking scheme has four blocking passes. The first blocking pass groups records that match on their ten-digit phone number. The second blocking pass groups records that match on the BCU ID³ and the first letter of the first and last name of the record. The third blocking pass groups records that match on the first letter of first and last name and on the month and day of birth. The fourth blocking pass groups records that match on state, county, area census office⁴, the first two letters of the first and last name, sex, and age grouping of ten-year intervals (e.g., 10-19, 20-29, 30-39, etc.). This blocking scheme scales to a nationwide deduplication task for the BigMatch software while reducing the amount of falsely discovered links to produce a manageable clerical review workload.

This blocking scheme was used for BigMatch and Splink. However, fastLink's built-in blocking functionality could not handle this volume of blocking for two main reasons. First, the number of variables used in the blocking prohibitively slowed down fastLink's blockData() function. Second, looping over many small blocks slowed fastLink's processing. We ended up using a modified blocking scheme for fastLink: pass 1 blocked on 3-digit phone area code, pass 2 blocked on state, pass 3 blocked on the first letter of first and last name, pass 4 blocked on sex and age groupings. Note that this modified blocking scheme is a superset of the original PES blocking scheme. This modified blocking scheme made fewer, bigger blocks and allowed for more comparison of other records, but this came with the drawback of potentially producing more false links. Table 1 summarizes the blocking schemes.

² basic collection units (BCUs) serve as the fundamental unit of work assignment for 2020 Census operations and decennial census field data collection. This is a small level of geography akin to a street block.

³ BCU ID is a unique identifier for a BCU.

⁴ Area Census Office is a temporary office established for Census data collection purposes in Census. These offices managed address listing field work, conducted local recruiting, and visited living quarters to conduct various Census operations.

Table 1: Blocking scheme used by matching software.

Scheme	Blocking variables			
	Pass 1	Pass 2	Pass 3	Pass 4
PES Blocking	10-digit phone	State County BCU ID First letter of first name First letter of last name	First letter of first name First letter of last name Month of birth Day of birth	State County Area census office First two letters of first name First two letters of last name Sex Age groupings
Modified Blocking	3-digit phone area code	State	First letter of first name First letter of last name	Sex Age groupings

The three software used the same attributes for matching: first name, middle initial, last name, month of birth, day of birth, and sex. The matching parameters for the F-S framework for fastLink and Splink were learned using their implementation of the E-M algorithm. BigMatch does not have any learning built into the software; the user must provide the model parameters. The parameters used for BigMatch were the same model parameters used during the 2020 PES matching. These parameters are also used as a control to see if there is any improvement in either fastLink's or Splink's implementation of the E-M algorithm. We ran fastLink's E-M algorithm on the sample set of person enumerations, that is, the 1,167,705 records in the United States (including Washington D.C.) and the 33,254 records in Puerto Rico. This run was supposed to yield a broad basis of agreement patterns across all matching attributes that would exist in the E-sample data with the intention to be then used on a nationwide deduplication of records. This was not done due to fastLink's computational limitations which will be discussed in the conclusion section. FastLink's E-M algorithm converged on this set of person records and these parameters were applied towards linking on the enumerated person records in the E sample BCUs for the comparative analysis. Using the DuckDB backend, Splink's E-M algorithm could not converge in a timely manner on the unblocked set of E-sample records. Splink did learn a set of matching parameters when restricted to the blocked set of the E-sample data.

Each of the three software produced a set of links for both the deduplication of the 1,167,705 enumerated person records in the United States (including Washington D.C.) and for the 33,254 enumerated person records in Puerto Rico. We defined a unique pair ID for the true set of links and applied that pair ID definition to the software output for comparison. These pair IDs from the software's output links were matched against the pair IDs found in the true set of links.

3. Results

The F-S framework requires a cutoff on the match score or match probability, where links with scores above the cutoff are kept. Since fastLink and Splink were allowed to learn their own set of model parameters and BigMatch used its predetermined model parameters, the cutoffs vary across software. We set the cutoffs to optimize the overall F1 score⁵. F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall⁶.

Figure 1: The left graph shows that BigMatch obtained the highest overall F1 score for the deduplication of the United States (including Washington D.C.). The right graph shows that BigMatch obtained the highest overall F1 score for the deduplication of Puerto Rico.

The graphs in Figure 1 show True positives + False positives on the horizontal axis; these are the number of links retained to obtain the optimal F1 score shown on the vertical axis. The more links held on by a software the more true links will be discovered, but at an eventual cost of picking up more falsely discovered links. This tradeoff occurs where the F1 scores start to decrease. The higher the F1 peak indicates the better the software did comparatively. Under an ideal classifier the peak F1 would be at 1 and this peak would occur at 3,941 for the United States (including Washington D.C.) test and at 1,125 for the Puerto Rico test.

Table 2 and Table 3 summarize the metrics precision, recall, and F1 score for each of the software at the cutoff that yields the maximum F1. Also included are the timing results from our tests for each of the software.

Table 2: The United States (including Washington D.C.) link quality across each software's optimal cutoff for F1.

Software	TIMING (sec)	PRECISION	RECALL	F1 Score
BigMatch	38	0.8733	0.7161	0.7869
fastLink	44161	0.9636	0.4568	0.6198
Splink	40	0.7325	0.6336	0.6795

⁵ $F1 = 2 * \frac{precision * recall}{precision + recall}$

⁶ $precision = \frac{tp}{tp + fp}$; $recall = \frac{tp}{tp + fn}$; where tp are true links, fp are false links, fn are undiscovered links.

Table 3: Puerto Rico link quality across each software’s optimal cutoff for F1.

Software	TIMING (sec)	PRECISION	RECALL	F1
BigMatch	1	0.9522	0.8277	0.8849
fastLink	7523	0.8905	0.6396	0.7445
Splink	11	0.71	0.8587	0.7773

For the United States (including Washington D.C.) results, BigMatch has the highest F1 score among the software compared, driven by the highest recall of true links. Splink has the second highest F1 score with its precision and recall closer to each other than the other software. FastLink has the lowest F1 score at its optimal cutoff; it did obtain the highest precision at its optimal cutoff point, but also has the lowest recall of true links found. Note: there could be bias in favor of BigMatch since the initial round of deduplication in the 2020 PES was done by a software that incorporates BigMatch, but there were more factors considered in dispositioning the final match status of a record in the clerical review. Also note that the clerical reviewer has several advantages in their ability to label a true link by taking a broader context such as household composition or the mover status, but still may include human error.

For the Puerto Rico results, BigMatch has the highest F1 score and the highest precision. Splink has the second highest F1 score and has the highest recall amongst the software. FastLink has the lowest F1 and the second highest precision.

Timing was measured for each software, to determine how the multithreaded software compared to the single-threaded BigMatch application. BigMatch ran on a single Central Processing Unit (CPU) core and was still able to complete the linking on the records faster than the other two software. Splink ran only using the DuckDB linker, analogous to a single thread, and was able to finish the linking around the same time frame as BigMatch. FastLink was able to run using 48 cores but was not able to finish linking within a timeframe close to either of the other two software.

4. Conclusions

The E-sample deduplication shows that the BigMatch software, under its existing set of matching parameters, was able to discover more duplicates within the E-sample person records while maintaining a relatively high precision compared to the other software. The timing of each software demonstrates the differences in computational speed between a compiled programming language such as C and an interpreted programming language such as R or Python.

There are other fastLink features to study including alternative blocking tools and options for string comparators, but ultimately with its current design fastLink is severely limited for linkage tasks with hundreds of millions of records. We found two major issues with scaling fastLink, both relating to the blocking scheme. First, because the scheme made many blocks, iterating a for loop over all the blocks was slow in execution. Second, under this scheme the blocks were imbalanced, and the imbalanced blocks did not perform well with OpenMP’s parallelization of the blocked computations. This issue was shown in the fastLink execution of the fastLink function having variation in number of cores used per a given block. If a block was big enough OpenMP would allocate the specified number of cores for processing, but if the block was smaller than the number of cores specified, OpenMP would allocate fewer cores for that block’s processing. This had a throttling effect on the fastLink runs and were unable to be controlled under the blocking scheme we used.

Splink also has features meriting further investigation, including its preprocessing and data visualization tools along with the various SQL backends. Splink’s ability to block with SQL

conditions made using and setting up the blocking scheme comparatively easy. The main limitation was our ability to set up an environment to utilize a backend such as PySpark to scale Splink's processing to deduplicate hundreds of millions of records.

Finally, both Splink's and fastLink's E-M algorithms modeled parameters learned from patterns in the data. Their model parameters did provide accurate links of true duplicates present in the data with low false discovery. But each software was limited in its ability to find a higher portion of true duplicates than BigMatch found.

5. References

- [1] Cleaton, M., J. Hall, R. Shipsey, Z. White, and K. Xhaferaj (2022), "A case study of using Splink: Census Duplicate Matching," Proceedings of Statistics Canada Symposium 2022. Data Disaggregation: Building a More Representative Data Portrait of Society.
- [2] Enamorado, T., B. Fifield, and K. Imai (2019), "Using a Probabilistic Model to Assist Merging of Large-Scale Administrative Records," American Political Science Review, Volume 113, Issue 2, May 2019, pp. 353 – 371.
- [3] Fellegi, I.P., and A. B. Sunter (1969), "A Theory for Record Linkage," Journal of the American Statistical Association, 64:328, 1183-1210.
- [4] Fortini, M., B. Liseo, A. Nuccitelli, and M. Scanu, On Bayesian record linkage. Res. Official Stat. 4, 185–198 (2001).
- [5] Jaro, M.A. (1989), "Advances in Record-Linkage Methodology as Applied to Matching the 1985 Census of Tampa, Florida," Journal of the American Statistical Association, 84:406, 414-420.
- [6] Kennel, T., "The Design of the Post-Enumeration Survey for the 2020 Census," DSSD 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey Memorandum Series #2020-B-01, U.S. Census Bureau, 2022.
- [7] Winkler, W., and Y. Thibaudeau (1991), "An Application of the Fellegi-Sunter Model of Record Linkage to the 1990 U.S. Decennial Census," U.S. Census Bureau, Research Report Series (#1991-09).
- [8] Yancey, W. (2007), "BigMatch: A Program for Extracting Probable Matches from a Large File," U.S. Census Bureau, Research Report Series (#2007-01).